

A formula for the values of the Riemann zeta function at positive even integers by means of the Euler beta function

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Abstract

In this short note, we derive a formula for the values of the Riemann zeta function at positive even integers. The identity can be seen as a product identity of the Euler beta function as well and it is convenient in the sense that it is rather compact and does not contain analytical limits or integrals explicitly.

Keywords: Riemann zeta function; product identity; Euler beta function; Euler gamma function

Mathematics Subject Classification (2020): 11M06, 33B15

1 Introduction

The Riemann zeta function poses an important function in analytical number theory. Hence, its properties are interesting for mathematicians, especially the values of the function at certain numbers are objects of research. One famous result is the identity

$$\zeta(2n) = (-1)^{n-1} \frac{(2\pi)^{2n}}{2(2n)!} B_{2n} \quad (1)$$

for all positive integers $n > 0$ [1], where different proofs for (1) or (1) for the case $n = 1$ has been provided so far (see e.g. [2, 5, 6, 7]) and where B_k denotes the k -th Bernoulli number for every positive integer $k > 0$.

Using a defining relation between the Euler beta function and the Euler gamma function, Gauss' multiplication formula for the Euler gamma function and (1), we derive a formula for $\zeta(2n)$ for all integers $n > 0$ that can also be seen as a product identity of the Euler beta function and which does not exist in the current mathematical literature to the best of the authors' knowledge.

2 Results

We want to start our considerations with some useful reminders. Let $z_1, z_2 \in \mathbb{C}$ with $Re(z_1) > 0$ and $Re(z_2) > 0$. We denote $B(z_1, z_2)$ as the value of the Euler beta function at $(z_1, z_2) \in \mathbb{C}^2$.

We remark that the important identity

$$B(z_1, z_2) = \frac{\Gamma(z_1)\Gamma(z_2)}{\Gamma(z_1 + z_2)} \quad (2)$$

holds [3]. Another useful identity is a variant of Gauss' multiplication formula for the Euler gamma function or, to be more precise,

$$\frac{(2\pi)^{\frac{n-1}{2}}}{n^{z-\frac{1}{2}}}\Gamma(z) = \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{z+k}{n}\right) \quad (3)$$

for all positive integers $n > 0$ and all $z \in \mathbb{C}$ with $Re(z) > 0$ [4]. Reminding

$$\Gamma(1) = 1,$$

(3) yields

$$\prod_{k=1}^{4n} \Gamma\left(\frac{k}{4n+1}\right) = \frac{(2\pi)^{2n}}{\sqrt{1+4n}} \quad (4)$$

for all integers $n > 0$.

Now, we can formulate and prove our main result, namely

Theorem 2.1. *All integers $n > 0$ satisfy*

$$\zeta(2n) = (-1)^{n-1} \frac{B_{2n}}{2n} \sqrt{n + \frac{1}{4}} \prod_{k=1}^{4n-1} B\left(\frac{k(k+1)}{8n+2}, \frac{k+1}{4n+1}\right).$$

Proof. Let $n > 0$ be an integer. (1) delivers

$$\zeta(2n) = \frac{(-1)^{n-1} 2^{2n-1}}{(2n)!} B_{2n} \pi^{2n}. \quad (5)$$

(5) and $B_{2n} \neq 0$ lead to

$$\frac{(2\pi)^{2n}}{\sqrt{1+4n}} = \frac{2 \cdot (2n)! \zeta(2n)}{(-1)^{n-1} \sqrt{1+4n} B_{2n}}. \quad (6)$$

(4) and (6) yield

$$\zeta(2n) = \frac{(-1)^{n-1} B_{2n} \sqrt{n + \frac{1}{4}}}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=1}^{4n} \Gamma\left(\frac{k}{4n+1}\right). \quad (7)$$

Set $A_r := \frac{r}{4n+1}$ for every $r \in \mathbb{N}$ with $1 \leq r \leq 4n$. (2) leads to

$$\prod_{k=1}^{4n-1} B\left(\sum_{l=1}^k A_l, A_{k+1}\right) = \prod_{k=1}^{4n-1} \frac{\Gamma\left(\sum_{l=1}^k A_l\right) \Gamma(A_{k+1})}{\Gamma\left(\sum_{l=1}^{k+1} A_l\right)}. \quad (8)$$

Considering the right-hand side of (8), one can see easily that

$$\prod_{k=1}^{4n-1} B\left(\sum_{l=1}^k A_l, A_{k+1}\right) = \frac{1}{\Gamma\left(\sum_{k=1}^{4n} A_k\right)} \prod_{k=1}^{4n} \Gamma(A_k)$$

and therefore

$$\prod_{k=1}^{4n} \Gamma\left(\frac{k}{4n+1}\right) = \Gamma\left(\sum_{k=1}^{4n} \frac{k}{4n+1}\right) \prod_{k=1}^{4n-1} B\left(\sum_{l=1}^k \frac{l}{4n+1}, \frac{k+1}{4n+1}\right) \quad (9)$$

hold. We recall the well-known identity

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{k}{4n+1} = \frac{m(m+1)}{8n+2} \quad (10)$$

for all $m \in \mathbb{N}$ with $m \geq 1$. (9) and (10) deliver

$$\prod_{k=1}^{4n} \Gamma\left(\frac{k}{4n+1}\right) = \Gamma(2n) \prod_{k=1}^{4n-1} B\left(\frac{k(k+1)}{8n+2}, \frac{k+1}{4n+1}\right). \quad (11)$$

(7), (11) and $\Gamma(2n) = (2n-1)!$ lead to

$$\zeta(2n) = (-1)^{n-1} \frac{B_{2n}}{2n} \sqrt{n + \frac{1}{4}} \prod_{k=1}^{4n-1} B\left(\frac{k(k+1)}{8n+2}, \frac{k+1}{4n+1}\right).$$

□

This result implies

Corollary 2.2. *All integers $n > 0$ satisfy*

$$\prod_{k=1}^{4n-1} B\left(\frac{k(k+1)}{8n+2}, \frac{k+1}{4n+1}\right) = \frac{(2\pi)^{2n}}{(2n-1)! \sqrt{1+4n}}.$$

Proof. (1) and Theorem 2.1 yield the claim. □

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Rouven Paul Jahnke for his productive comments regarding this note.

Declaration of interests

The authors do not have any conflict of interest concerning this note.

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